

ON THE IRRATIONALITY OF A DIVISOR FUNCTION SERIES

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Abstract

Here, we show, unconditionally for $k = 3$, and on the prime k -tuples conjecture for $k \geq 4$, that $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sigma_k(n)}{n!}$ is irrational, where $\sigma_k(n)$ denotes the sum of the k th powers of the divisors of n .

1. Introduction

For a positive integer n put

$$\sigma_k(n) = \sum_{d|n} d^k$$

for the sum of the k th powers of the (positive) divisors of n . In [4], Erdős and Kac showed that the series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sigma_k(n)}{n!}$$

is irrational for both $k = 1$ and $k = 2$. The problem is mentioned also in [5], wherein it is stated that the method does not seem to extend to $k \geq 3$, and it appears as B14 in [6]. Let

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us quickly give proofs of the irrationality of these series when $k = 0, 1, 2$. Assume that the given series is A/B , where A and B are positive integers. Multiplying by $(n - 1)!$, where $n > B$, we get that

$$\sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \sigma_k(j) \frac{(n-1)!}{j!} + \frac{\sigma_k(n)}{n} + \frac{\sigma_k(n+1)}{n(n+1)} + \sum_{j \geq 2} \frac{\sigma_k(n+j)}{n(n+1) \cdots (n+j)} = \frac{A(n-1)!}{B}.$$

The first of the above sums is an integer and the right hand side is also an integer. The second sum is positive and, for $k \leq 2$, its size is

$$\leq \frac{\sigma_2(n+2)}{n(n+1)(n+2)} + \sum_{j \geq 3} \frac{\sigma_2(n+j)}{n(n+1) \cdots (n+j)} \ll \frac{1}{n} + \sum_{m \geq n} \frac{1}{m^2} \ll \frac{1}{n},$$

so that this term belongs to the interval $[0, c/n]$, where c is an absolute constant. We shall take n to be a prime $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ such that $(n+1)/2$ has no prime factor $< y$, where y is a large positive real number. Such primes exist by Dirichlet's theorem on primes in arithmetical progressions. Then

$$\frac{\sigma_1(n+1)}{n(n+1)} \leq \frac{c_1 \log \log n}{n}$$

for some constant c_1 , and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{5}{4} &\leq \frac{\sigma_2(n+1)}{n(n+1)} \leq \frac{5(n+1)}{4n} \prod_{q \geq y} \left(1 + \frac{1}{q^2} + \cdots\right) \\ &\leq \frac{5(n+1)}{4n} \exp\left(\sum_{q \geq y} \frac{1}{q(q-1)}\right) = \frac{5(n+1)}{4n} e^{O(1/y)} \\ &= \frac{5}{4} + O\left(\frac{1}{y}\right) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

whenever $n > y$. Thus, when $k = 1$, we get that $\sigma_1(n)/n = 1 + 1/n$, and we conclude that there is an integer in the interval $[1/n, (c+1+c_1 \log \log n)/n]$, while when $k = 2$ we get that $\sigma_2(n)/n = n+1/n$, and so there exists an integer in the interval $[1/4, 1/4+c/n+c_2/y]$, where c_2 is the constant implied by the O symbol in (1). Choosing n (and y) to be sufficiently large, we get a contradiction in the case $k = 1$ (and $k = 2$), which completes the proof.

In this paper, we make a modest contribution to the problem, proving two results about the irrationality of the above series for $k \geq 3$.

Theorem 1. *The sum of the series*

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sigma_3(n)}{n!} \tag{2}$$

is irrational.

We recall the statement of the *Prime k -tuples Conjecture* (see [3, 7, 9]), which is due to Dickson.

Conjecture 1. *For any $k \geq 2$, let a_1, \dots, a_k and b_1, \dots, b_k be integers with $a_i > 0$ for each $i = 1, \dots, k$. Suppose that for every prime number p there exists an integer n such that $\prod_{i=1}^k (a_i n + b_i)$ is not a multiple of p . Then there exist infinitely many positive integers n such that $p_i = a_i n + b_i$ is prime for all $i = 1, \dots, k$.*

We have the following result for any positive integer k .

Theorem 2. *The Prime k -tuples Conjecture implies that*

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sigma_k(n)}{n!}$$

is irrational.

Throughout this paper, we use the Landau symbols O and o as well as Vinogradov's symbols \gg , \ll and \asymp with their regular meaning. The constants implied by these symbols depend at most on k . We use p and q to denote prime numbers.

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2. Proof of Theorem 1

Our main tool is the following well-known theorem of Chen (see [1], [2]).

Theorem 3. *Let a be an integer. There exists x_a such that for $x > x_a$, the interval $[x/2, x]$ contains $\gg x a / \varphi(a)^2 (\log x)^2$ prime numbers $p \equiv 1 \pmod{a}$ such that $q = (p + 1)/2$ is either a prime or a product of two primes each one of which exceeds $x^{1/10}$.*

A proof containing the basic ideas for this theorem appears, for example, in Chapter 11 of [8]. Chen actually proved that for large even integers N there are $\gg N / (\log N)^2$ primes p such that $N - p$ is either a prime or a product of two large primes. Easy and well-known modifications of Chen's argument yield the above theorem.

To prove our Theorem 1 we assume that the sum of the series shown at (2) is rational and deduce a contradiction. We write it, as we did for $k = 0, 1$ and 2 as A/B , multiply

across by $(n - 1)!$ for some large n (with $n > B$), and obtain

$$\frac{\sigma_3(n)}{n} + \frac{\sigma_3(n + 1)}{n(n + 1)} + \frac{\sigma_3(n + 2)}{n(n + 1)(n + 2)} + \sum_{j \geq 3} \frac{\sigma_3(n + j)}{n(n + 1) \cdots (n + j)} = (n - 1)! \left(\frac{A}{B} - \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \frac{\sigma_k(j)}{j!} \right), \tag{3}$$

where the right hand side is an integer. In what follows, we shall exploit the above relation. Since $\sigma_3(n) \ll n^3$, we have

$$\sum_{j \geq 3} \frac{\sigma_3(n + j)}{n(n + 1) \cdots (n + j)} \ll \frac{1}{n} + \sum_{m \geq n} \frac{1}{m^2} \ll \frac{1}{n}.$$

Furthermore, the sum appearing on the left hand side of formula (3) above is a positive integer. We now let y be a large positive real number which we shall fix later, and take $a = 72 \prod_{5 \leq p \leq y} p$. Note that, by Chebyshev’s bounds, this means that $y \asymp \log a$. We let x be large compared to a and $m \in [x/2a, x/a]$ be such that $p = am + 1$ is prime and $q = (p + 1)/2 = (am + 2)/2$ is either a prime or a product of two primes $q_1 q_2$ each exceeding $x^{1/10}$. Choose n to be the prime $n = p$. We then note that

$$\frac{\sigma_3(n)}{n} = n^2 + \frac{1}{n}.$$

Furthermore, writing $n + 2 = am + 3 = 3t$, we have that t is coprime to all primes $q \leq y$, and so obtain the inequalities

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{28}{27} < \frac{\sigma_3(n + 2)}{n(n + 1)(n + 2)} &= \frac{28}{27} \frac{\sigma_3(t)}{t^3} \left(1 + O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right) \right) \\ &< \frac{28}{27} \prod_{p > y} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^3} \right)^{-1} \left(1 + O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right) \right) \\ &< 1 + \frac{1}{27} + O\left(\frac{1}{y^2}\right), \end{aligned}$$

since $y < \sqrt{x}$. Combining this with our estimate for the tail of the series we have, for n a prime as above,

$$\frac{\sigma_3(n)}{n} + \frac{\sigma_3(n + 2)}{n(n + 1)(n + 2)} + \sum_{j \geq 3} \frac{\sigma_3(n + j)}{n(n + 1) \cdots (n + j)} = A_n + \frac{1}{27} + O\left(\frac{1}{y^2}\right), \tag{4}$$

where A_n is a positive integer.

We now consider the remaining term $\sigma_3(n + 1)/(n(n + 1))$.

Assume first that for some large x there is a prime $p = am + 1 \in [x/2, x]$ such that $q = (p + 1)/2 = (a/2)m + 1$ is prime. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\sigma_3(n + 1)}{n(n + 1)} &= \frac{\sigma_3(2q)}{2q(2q - 1)} = \frac{9(q^3 + 1)}{2q(2q - 1)} \\ &= \frac{9}{4}q + \frac{9}{8} + \frac{9q - 4}{8q(2q - 1)} = B_n + \frac{3}{8} + O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right) \end{aligned}$$

with some integer B_n , where we have used the fact that $q = (a/2)m + 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, because $8 \mid a$. Summing up everything, we find that

$$\frac{1}{27} + \frac{3}{8} + O\left(\frac{1}{y^2}\right) \in \mathbb{Z},$$

which is impossible if y is chosen to be sufficiently large.

So, we are left with the more interesting part of the problem where $q = q_1q_2$, where $q_1 > q_2 > x^{1/10}$ holds for all the $\gg xa/\varphi(a)^2(\log x)^2$ choices of primes $p = am + 1 \in [x/2, x]$ guaranteed by Chen's Theorem 3.

We put

$$M = \left\lfloor \frac{\sigma_3(n+1)}{n(n+1)} \right\rfloor = \left\lfloor \frac{9\sigma_3(q)}{2q(2q-1)} \right\rfloor.$$

Note that since $q_2 \leq q^{1/2}$, we have that

$$\frac{\sigma_3(q)}{2q(2q-1)} = \frac{q^3 + q_1^3 + q_2^3 + 1}{2q(2q-1)} = \frac{q^3 + q_1^3 + O(q^{3/2})}{2q(2q-1)} = \frac{q^3 + q_1^3}{2q(2q-1)} + O\left(\frac{1}{q^{1/2}}\right).$$

Thus, using also the previous calculations of fractional parts (see (4)), we find that for large x ,

$$M + \frac{26}{27} - \frac{c_0}{y^2} \leq \frac{9q^3 + 9q_1^3}{2q(2q-1)} \leq M + \frac{26}{27} + \frac{c_0}{y^2}$$

holds for all large x with some constant $c_0 > 0$, an inequality which can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} & q^2 \left(4M + 3 - 9q + \frac{23}{27} - \frac{2q(m + O(1))}{q^2} - \frac{4c_0}{y^2} \right) \leq 9q_1^3 \\ & \leq q^2 \left(4M + 3 - 9q + \frac{23}{27} - \frac{2q(m + O(1))}{q^2} + \frac{4c_0}{y^2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

From this inequality and the fact that $q_1 < qx^{-1/10}$, we find that

$$\frac{M}{q} = \frac{9(q^3 + q_1^3)}{2q^2(2q-1)} + O\left(\frac{1}{q}\right) = \frac{9}{4} + O\left(\frac{1}{x^{3/10}}\right)$$

so

$$-\frac{2q(M + O(1))}{q^2} = -\frac{9}{2} + O\left(\frac{1}{x^{3/10}}\right).$$

Hence, we deduce that

$$4M + 3 - 9q + \frac{23}{27} - \frac{2q(M + O(1))}{q^2} = L + \frac{19}{54} + O\left(\frac{1}{x^{3/10}}\right)$$

holds with some non-negative integer L . Thus, for large x , provided that $y < x^{3/20}$, we get that

$$\frac{q^2}{9} \left(L + \frac{19}{54} - \frac{5c_0}{y^2} \right) < q_1^3 < \frac{q^2}{9} \left(L + \frac{19}{54} + \frac{5c_0}{y^2} \right),$$

which is equivalent to

$$\frac{q_2^2}{9} \left(L + \frac{19}{54} - \frac{5c_0}{y^2} \right) < q_1 < \frac{q_2^2}{9} \left(L + \frac{19}{54} + \frac{5c_0}{y^2} \right). \tag{5}$$

The above inequalities certainly tell us that $L \geq 0$, provided that y is sufficiently large. Further, the left hand side of the above inequality is $> q_2^2/27$ if $y^2 > 220c_0$, so if y satisfies the above inequality and x is large, then $q_2^2/27 \leq q_1 \leq x/q_2$, and therefore $q_2 \leq 3x^{1/3}$. Now fix q_2 . Then the left hand side of the above inequality is $\geq (L + 1/3)q_2^2/27$ and the middle term satisfies $q_1 \leq x/q_2$. Thus, $L + 1/3 \leq 27x/q_2^3$. Since $L \geq 0$ is an integer, it follows that the number of possibilities for L is

$$1 + \left\lfloor \frac{27x}{q_2^3} \right\rfloor \leq \frac{81x}{q_2^3}. \tag{6}$$

We now fix also $L \geq 0$. Then q_1 is a prime in the interval shown at (5) above such that $q_1q_2 \equiv 1 \pmod{a}$ and $2q_1q_2 - 1 = p$ is a prime. By the Brun sieve, the number of such primes is

$$\ll \frac{c_0q_2^2}{y^2} \cdot \left(\frac{a}{\varphi(a)^2} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{(\log(10c_0q_2^2/(9y^2a)))^2}.$$

Since $q_2 > x^{1/10}$, it follows that for large x we have $10c_0q_2^2/(9y^2a) > x^{1/6}$. Thus, the number of possibilities for q_1 once q_2 and L are fixed is

$$\ll \frac{1}{y^2} \cdot \frac{a}{\varphi(a)^2} \cdot \frac{q_2^2}{(\log x)^2}.$$

Summing up over all the possibilities for L shown at (6), we get that the total number of possibilities for q_1 when q_2 is fixed is

$$\ll \frac{1}{y^2} \cdot \frac{a}{\varphi(a)^2} \cdot \frac{x}{(\log x)^2} \cdot \frac{1}{q_2},$$

and now summing up the above bound over all primes $q_2 \in [x^{1/10}, 3x^{1/3}]$, we get that the total number of possibilities for p is

$$\ll \frac{1}{y^2} \frac{a}{\varphi(a)^2} \frac{x}{(\log x)^2} \sum_{x^{1/10} \leq q_2 \leq 3x^{1/3}} \frac{1}{q_2} \ll \frac{1}{y^2} \frac{a}{\varphi(a)^2} \frac{x}{(\log x)^2}, \tag{7}$$

where the fact that the last sum above is $O(1)$ follows from Mertens's estimate for the summatory function of the reciprocal of the primes. Let c_1 be the constant implied in the Vinogradov symbol from Chen's Theorem 3 and c_2 be the constant implied in the last Vinogradov symbol in (7). Comparing the estimates for the number of primes p under scrutiny we get

$$\frac{c_1ax}{\varphi(a)^2(\log x)^2} \leq \frac{c_2ax}{\varphi(a)^2y^2(\log x)^2}$$

leading to $y^2 < c_3$, where $c_3 = c_2/c_1$. Choosing y larger than this we complete the proof of Theorem 1.

3. Proof of Theorem 2

Let $k \geq 4$. For $i = 1, \dots, k$ we let $Q_i(X), R_i(X) \in \mathbb{Z}[X]$ be the polynomials given by the division algorithm:

$$(X + i)^k = Q_i(X)(X + 1) \cdots (X + i) + R_i(X) \quad i = 1, \dots, k,$$

where $\deg Q_i(X) = k - i$ and $\deg R_i(X) \leq i - 1$. Note that when $i = k$ we have that $Q_k(X) = 1$. For each of those $i = 1, \dots, k$ for which $Q_i(-i) \neq 0$ choose distinct primes $p_i > k$ such that $p_i \nmid \sigma_k(i)Q_i(-i)$. (For any other i , for notational purposes, take $p_i = 1$.) As we have seen, $Q_k(-k) = 1 \neq 0$, so that $p_k \nmid \sigma_k(k)Q_k(-k)$ can be arranged simply by choosing $p_k > \sigma_k(k)$.

Let $P = \prod_{i=1}^k p_i$ and let m be a positive integer such that

$$\frac{(k!)^2}{i}m + 1 \equiv p_i \pmod{p_i^2} \quad i = 1, \dots, k.$$

By the Chinese Remainder Theorem, there are infinitely many such positive integers m and they form the arithmetic progression $m_0 \pmod{P^2}$, where m_0 is the first positive integer in this progression. Given such an m , we choose $n = (k!)^2m$ and write $m = m_0 + \ell P^2$ with some nonnegative integer ℓ . Then

$$n + i = i \left(\frac{(k!)^2}{i}m + 1 \right) = ip_i \left(\frac{(k!)^2}{i} \frac{P^2}{p_i} \ell + \frac{(k!)^2 m_0 / i + 1}{p_i} \right).$$

Put

$$A_i = \frac{(k!)^2}{i} \frac{P^2}{p_i} \quad \text{and} \quad B_i = \frac{(k!)^2 m_0 / i + 1}{p_i}$$

for $i = 1, \dots, k$.

One checks easily that we can apply the Prime k -tuples Conjecture 1 to the linear polynomials $A_i \ell + B_i$. Indeed, the prime numbers dividing A_i are exactly the primes $p \leq k$ together with the primes p_i . Since $B_i \mid (k!)^2 m_0 / i + 1$, we see that B_i is coprime to all primes $p \leq k$. Further, $B_i \equiv 1 \pmod{p_i}$ from the way m_0 was chosen. To see that B_i is coprime to p_j if $j \neq i$ assume otherwise. Then $p_j \mid ((k!)^2 / j)m_0 + 1$ and $p_j \mid B_i \mid ((k!)^2 / i)m_0 + 1$. Hence, $p_j \mid (k!)^2 m_0 + j$ and $p_j \mid (k!)^2 m_0 + i$, so $p_j \mid (j - i)$, but this is false because $p_j > k$. Thus, the conditions for the applicability of the Prime k -tuples Conjecture 1 are fulfilled and we can let ℓ be large and such that $A_i \ell + B_i = q_i$ are all primes for $i = 1, \dots, k$. Put $a_i = ip_i$ and note that if $m = m_0 + \ell P^2$, then $n + i = a_i q_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, k$.

Now assume that the series

$$\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sigma_k(j)}{j!} = \frac{A}{B}$$

with A and B coprime integers. Suppose n is sufficiently large, and in particular $n > B$. Multiplying across by $n!$, we get

$$\sum_{j \geq n} \sigma_k(j) \frac{n!}{j!} + \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{\sigma_k(n+i)}{(n+1) \cdots (n+i)} + \sum_{j \geq k+1} \frac{\sigma_k(n+j)}{(n+1) \cdots (n+j)} \in \mathbb{Z}. \tag{8}$$

The first sum above is an integer, while the last sum is positive and, since $\sigma_k(n) \ll n^k$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j \geq k+1} \frac{\sigma_k(n+j)}{(n+1) \cdots (n+j)} &= \frac{\sigma_k(n+k+1)}{(n+1) \cdots (n+k+1)} + \sum_{j \geq k+2} \frac{\sigma_k(n+j)}{(n+1) \cdots (n+j)} \\ &\ll \frac{1}{n} + \sum_{j \geq k+2} \frac{1}{(n+j)^2} \ll \frac{1}{n}. \end{aligned}$$

As for the intermediate terms, since q_i is prime we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\sigma_k(n+i)}{(n+1) \cdots (n+i)} &= \frac{\sigma_k(a_i)(q_i^k + 1)}{(n+1) \cdots (n+i)} \\ &= \frac{\sigma_k(a_i)}{a_i^k} \left(\frac{(n+i)^k + a_i^k}{(n+1) \cdots (n+i)} \right) \\ &= \frac{\sigma_k(a_i)}{a_i^k} \left(Q_i(n) + \frac{R_i(n) + a_i^k}{(n+1) \cdots (n+i)} \right) \\ &= \frac{\sigma_k(a_i)}{a_i^k} Q_i(n) + O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where for the above error term we used the fact that $\deg R_i \leq i - 1$. Since $n \equiv -i \pmod{p_i}$, we get that $Q_i(n) \equiv Q_i(-i) \pmod{p_i}$ so that $Q_i(n) = Q_i(-i) + p_i \ell_i(n)$, for some integers $\ell_i(n)$. Thus,

$$\frac{\sigma_k(n+i)}{(n+1) \cdots (n+i)} = \frac{\sigma_k(ip_i)}{(ip_i)^k} (Q_i(-i) + \ell_i(n)p_i) + O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right).$$

We add everything together, multiply formula (8) by $(k!)^k P^{k-1}$ and get

$$\sum_{i=1}^k P_i^{k-1} \sigma_k(ip_i) \frac{(k!)^k}{i^k} \frac{1}{p_i} (Q_i(-i) + p_i \ell_i(n)) + O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right) \in \mathbb{Z},$$

where

$$P_i = P p_i^{-1} = \prod_{\substack{1 \leq j \leq k \\ j \neq i}} p_j.$$

From this it follows that

$$\sum_{i=1}^k P_i^{k-1} \frac{(k!)^k}{i^k} \frac{\sigma_k(ip_i) Q_i(-i)}{p_i} + O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right) \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

At this moment, we observe that the sum on the left does not depend on n and so

$$\sum_{1 \leq i \leq k} P_i^{k-1} \frac{(k!)^k}{i^k} \frac{\sigma_k(ip_i)}{p_i} Q_i(-i) \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

Using also the fact that $\sigma_k(ip_i) = \sigma_k(i)\sigma_k(p_i) = \sigma_k(i)(p_i^k + 1)$, we get that the above relation implies

$$\sum_{1 \leq i \leq k} P_i^{k-1} \frac{(k!)^k}{i^k} \frac{\sigma_k(i)}{p_i} Q_i(-i) \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

This is a non-empty (since $Q_k(-k) = 1$) sum of non-zero rational numbers whose reduced denominators are distinct primes. Thus, the above sum cannot be an integer. The proof of Theorem 2 is complete.

Note Added: March 2007. Shortly after this paper was submitted, we learned about the recent appearance of the paper [10], where the same two results as the present ones have been obtained. The proof of the case $k = 3$ in [10] also uses sieve methods but is rather different, whereas the conditional proof for larger k 's is similar to ours. We thank Professor Igor Shparlinski for pointing out this reference to us.

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